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DUAL EDUCATION AS A WAY TO SOLVE MODERN PROBLEMS IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE PHILOLOGISTS IN THE FRENCH LANGUAGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF UKRAINE

Abstract.

Innovations became especially relevant with the beginning of a large-scale war unleashed by the Russian on the territory of UKRAINE, when it became vital to make quick, non-standard, essentially innovative decisions. The functioning of the education system in the conditions of martial law is characterized by an intensive search for new approaches to practical learning, innovative forms of organization of the educational process, effective pedagogical and information technologies for the combination of theory and practice of training future philologists in French in higher education.

Dual education contributes to the professional formation of an individual, its development and self-determination, the formation of readiness to perform professional actions. With this form of education, the acquisition of professional competencies takes place during the performance of practical actions, and the development of the personality – in the conditions of differentiated training. The prospects of the dual form of education are explained by the mutual interest of the state, the educational institution and the organization in the training of high-quality specialists.

Keywords: *competencies, professional training, dual education, foreign language competence, professional and communicative competence.*

High-quality education is one of the main aspects that enable graduates to be competitive in the labor market. The problems of higher education that Ukrainian institutions of higher education are facing today do not allow students to realize their potential within the walls of their own universities. Moreover, the qualifications possessed by bachelors of philology in French upon graduation from university are often not sufficient to meet the needs of employers. One of the ways to make the education system more effective for both students and higher education institutions is the concept of dual education. Dual education is designed to bring the education system to the requirements of the labor market, create opportunities to provide modern competencies to graduates of higher education institutions, and increase the competitiveness of both graduates and higher education institutions themselves in the conditions of the globalization of the education system. The competitiveness of any state on the world market and the quality of life of its population directly depend on the level of professional training of personnel [1].

One of the leading world leaders in the field of training of qualified personnel today is the European Union, which owes to this dual system of professional education and training. Dual education (from the Latin Dual is – double) is a type of education in which the training of individuals in educational institutions is combined with training at workplaces in enterprises, institutions and organizations to acquire a certain qualification. The main task of introducing elements of the dual form of education is to eliminate the main shortcomings of traditional forms and methods of training future philologists in the French language, to overcome the gap between theory and practice, education and practical activity, and to improve the quality of training

of qualified personnel taking into account the requirements of employers within the framework of new organizational – excellent forms of education. The theoretical part of a specialist's training takes place on the basis of an educational institution, and the practical part – at the workplace. Students combine studies and internships in the organization. At the same time, organizations order a higher education institution for a specific number of philologists of certain language specialty (for example, philologists of the French language), employers participate in the formation of the educational program. For their part, employers can have various forms of participation in the training of relevant specialists – they fully pay for training; purchase equipment; cover all expenses related to the process of their practical training; pay monetary rewards to students for the use of their work, etc [2].

That is why it is necessary to promote the further development of the export of elements of the dual form of training of qualified specialists and accelerate the introduction of its elements into the higher education system of Ukraine. In order to effectively introduce a dual form of higher education, it is necessary to clearly establish the rights and obligations of the higher education institution, employers and students.

Educator:

- must be responsible for the implementation of the curriculum in accordance with the schedule of the educational process;
- must comply with the charter of the institution of higher education and the provisions of the organization's corporate policy;
- must maintain contact with the coordinators of the dual form of education program;

- has the right to demand compliance with the rules of safety equipment and a dignified attitude towards oneself and, in case of violation of these rules, to sue for the protection of one's rights in accordance with the current legislation of Ukraine.

Institution of higher education:

- ensures high-quality theoretical training, the integrity of the educational program and compliance with education standards;

- is responsible for establishing cooperation with employers, as well as further effective communication of the parties;

- carries out the selection of the organization for dual education in accordance with the standards of the educational program;

- develops and approves the curriculum in accordance with the professional standard and the needs of employers;

- ensures coordination with the employer of the content of the theoretical and practical part of the training;

- provides training support for the student in the organization;

- together with the representative of the organization accepts reports and evaluates the quality of student training.

Employer:

- can initiate the establishment of cooperation with an educational institution regarding the training of specialists in a dual form of education;

- must meet the defined criteria for the organization that provides places for practical training under the dual form of education;

- is responsible for safety equipment and labor protection at the place of practice;

- participates in the development of educational programs and the curriculum of student training;

- participates in the selection of students for dual education;

- participates in the evaluation of the practical work of the student;

- provides a workplace to an education seeker in the organization for the internship period;

- assigns a qualified mentor to the student;

- provides the necessary resources and informational materials to perform the work of an education seeker;

- creates the necessary social and household conditions and opportunities for the student to implement an individual curriculum.

Ways and methods of solving problems:

- development of a model of beneficial relations between higher education institutions and employers, aimed at end-to-end practical training of students for independent professional activity by profession;

- establishment of an equal partnership of higher education institutions, employers and students with the aim of the latter gaining practical experience in the conditions of real professional activity through the introduction of a dual form of education;

- the dual form of obtaining education should unite the interest of employers, educational institutions and students as training of future specialists [3;4].

But at the same time, attention should be paid to the problematic areas of the introduction of dual education in institutions of higher education for the training of future philologists in the French language: lack of domestic experience, methods of combining theoretical and practical education, imperfection and instability of the labor market, complete unpreparedness of practice bases for such innovative integration processes in higher education, reluctance to cooperate and take responsibility for the training of young personnel.

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